

Stepwise hydrogelation of a naphthalene diimide appended peptide amphiphile and its application in cell-imaging and intracellular pH sensing

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Abstract

This study reports the self-assembly and application of a naphthalene diimide (NDI)-appended peptide amphiphile (PA). H-bonding between the peptide moiety in conjunction with π - π interactions between NDI and hydrophobic interactions are major driving forces behind the stepwise aggregation to form hydrogel. The PA in three

among
stacking
the
self-

assembly steps, produced efficient self-assemblies in water at physiological conditions, forming nanofibrous network which further formed self-supportive hydrogel. Importantly, this water soluble conjugate was found to be non-toxic, cell permeable and was used for cell imaging at very low concentration and has an extended biological application to assess intracellular pH. The relatively good biocompatibility and intracellular pH determining capability suggest it as a promising candidate for use as a supramolecular material in biomedical applications.

Hydrogelation, Naphthalene Diimide, Peptide Amphiphile

References

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